

Organizational Commitment and Teacher Effectiveness by Transformative Leadership

Vinit Singhal

Bharat Institute of Technology Meerut, India

Surbhi Agarwal

Hi-Tech Institute of Engineering and Technology, India

Usha Pandey

Institute of Applied Medicines and Research, Ghaziabad, India

Ashwini Mehta

MGGCPS, Indore, MP, India

Nayana Shree S

Bangalore City University, India

Minerva Das

*Faculty of Management Studies CMS Business School
JAIN (Deemed-to-be University), India*

Abstract: The effectiveness of teachers has a big impact on keeping and raising educational standards. This study sets out to demonstrate the beneficial effects of organisational passion and commitment on teacher effectiveness. In this study, a sample of 500 graduate school teachers in Delhi NCR served as the research population. While the data analysis method used SEM-PLS, or structural equation modelling, the sample method used multistage random sampling. The study's findings suggest that enhancing organisational commitment and culture as well as consistently putting transformational leadership into practise could increase teacher effectiveness. Also, it has demonstrated that organisational commitment and culture have a positive and significant influence as mediating factors.

Keywords: Organizational commitment, teaching effectiveness, transformative leadership

1. Introduction

By bringing on experienced and skilled teachers, education quality can be improved. The fundamental goal of regulations governing lecturers and professors is to raise the bar for education, especially for teachers. The law's objective was to enhance educators'

professionalism, credentials, and competency as well as their rights and responsibilities in order to promote their best performance. For education to be of greater quality, teacher performance needs to be improved. The improvement in instructors' performance is determined by organisational culture and leadership growth in schools, as well as the availability of favourable learning environments. This is due to the fact that organisational culture and the type of leadership employed in the organisation are among the factors that influence how each individual works (Robbins and Judge, 2015). According to several studies, the availability of learning support resources, company culture, and leadership style all contribute to teachers performing at a higher level (Olaleye, 2013; Hutabarat et al., 2015). Working involvement mediated the impact of these factors on teacher performance in addition to their favourable effects on organisational culture, leadership, and personal traits (Arifin et al., 2014). Yet, the majority of India's secondary schools continued to experience issues with subpar teacher performance.

Because enhancing individual performance in an organisation may be accomplished through individual approach, groups, and systems, maximising teacher performance requires a complete approach (Robbins and Judge, 2015). Because of this, factors including organisational dedication, business culture, and leadership style had an impact on teachers' performance both directly and indirectly.

According to the premise that many factors may affect a person's behaviour inside an organisation, organisational commitment and organisational culture were added as mediating variables for the influence of transformational leadership towards teacher performance (Robbins and Judge, 2015). However it is clear that a range of factors, both directly and indirectly, interact to significantly affect each person's working behaviour. The strength of each variable's influence on working behaviour was not taken into consideration by the hypothesis. The study's findings, which were in accordance with the theory, showed that transformational leadership had a favourable impact on organizational commitment and performance (Kala'lembang et al., 2015). Tremal et al. (2015) shown through their research how transformative leadership impacted performance. So, a variety of factors with intricate patterns of interaction have an effect on a person's success within an organization.

The explanation from previously acted as a guide for formulating the research problems: Can transformative leadership lead to an improvement in teachers' performance? Does the organisational culture, as led by transformational leadership, have a positive and significant impact on teachers' performance? Does a company's dedication to transformational leadership have a positive and noticeable impact on the performance of its teachers?

2. Literature Review

Performance refers to the amount or caliber of work one completes while performing their profession (Luthans, 2015). Another meaning of performance is notes made as a result of specific works or activities during a specific time period (Bernardin and Russel, 2013). Performance is the ability of a worker to produce results in line with organisational norms.

The amount of work, the quality of the job, the understanding of the work, the comments or remarks given, the judgements made, and the work planning in accordance with the scope of the duties assigned to him are only a few ways to assess performance (Dessler, 2013). However, not all performance assessment criteria are employed to evaluate an individual's performance. It is without a doubt necessary to modify this for the job type being evaluated. Teaching performance and management performance are the two forms of performance that must be met in the context of teacher performance assessment. Teaching performance is required to connect with pedagogical issues, whereas management performance is typically focused on supporting a competency portfolio based on planning, execution, and work control (Wendy, 2006). If the leader is successful in fulfilling his role, then individual performance may be at its highest. Ability to use the appropriate leadership style based on the traits of one's followers is a factor in a leader's performance. This is because the team members' ability to effectively connect with the leader (Robbins and Judge, 2015). Conclusions of the study demonstrate how organisational culture and transformational leadership impact instructors' efficacy (Arifin, 2014; Triwahyuni et.al., 2014).

Masa'deh et al. (2015).s study also shown that both transformational and transactional leadership had a positive impact on employee performance, which in turn enhanced corporate success. Thus, transformational leadership is a crucial factor in determining how well instructors execute. Employees are eager to put in extra effort when leaders and followers collaborate to increase morale and motivation, even if there are no obvious external benefits (Burns, 2007). This is an example of transformative leadership in action. The four cornerstones of transformational leadership are ideal influence, personalized care, inspiring drive, and intellectual stimulation (Bass et al., 2011).

Organizational culture, dedication, and transformative leadership are a few factors that can boost performance. When a group of individuals learns how to solve problems, adapt to their external environment, and integrate with their internal environment, an organization's culture can be established (Schein, 2010). Together with the external environment, the company's strategy, and its objectives, cultural values that are significant to the organisation must also be taken into account. Many studies have shown that the four cultural forms of ability, achievement, clan, and bureaucracy and the two components of strategy and environment are related (Daft, 2010).

Organizational commitment refers to the psychological ties that people have when they support the aims of the organisation, uphold their own beliefs, and genuinely want to stay a part of it. Organizational commitment, as defined by Allen et al. (2017), is composed of three organisational components: affective commitment, continuous commitment, and normative commitment. When working conditions are psychologically satisfying, employee commitment rises. Employee involvement and efforts to improve the organization's performance and goals therefore increase (Chaikambang, 2016). Research indicates that the relationship between transformative leadership theories and employee performance is moderated by organisational commitment (Almutairi, 2016). The existence of employees in a company is a determinant in the rise of productivity. As a result, managers must create loyalty among their workers. More production and fewer employee absenteeism are often outcomes of high organisational commitment (Rosa and Ancok, 2020).

The results of past studies, which demonstrated that a range of factors influenced employee performance, served as the foundation for this study. The results of Hutabarat's (2015) study showed how organisational culture affected job satisfaction and motivation, which in turn affected work performance. Studies show that organisational culture has a substantial impact on employee performance and productivity in emerging economies (Uddin et.al., 2015). As a result, a number of variables, including organisational culture and transformational leadership, have an effect on a person's success within an organisation. Yet, the impact of each independent element on performance differs in strength. The uniqueness of this study lies in the manner the model was developed, which takes corporate culture and commitment as mediating variables and employs transformational leadership as a predictor of teacher performance. This model's construction represents an idea's progression and represents a substantial break from past research. Thus, it is possible to formulate the research hypothesis as follows:

H1: The effectiveness of teachers is significantly impacted favorably by transformational leadership.

H2: Through corporate culture, transformational leadership significantly improves teacher performance.

H3: By organisational commitment, transformational leadership significantly improves teacher performance.

3. Methodology

3.1. Measurement of Variables

Transformational leadership is the ability of a leader to motivate, inspire, and assist team

members in realizing organizational goals. Transformational leadership is characterized by intellectual stimulation, interpersonal concern, inspirational motivation, and ideal influence. An organization's culture is defined as the set of values or standards that its members accept, uphold, and grow. Junior high schools and the instructors that work there have a strong relationship, and they are willing to work together to achieve the institution's objectives. Organizational commitment indicators include things like normative commitment, continuance commitment, and affective commitment.

A teacher's performance as a teacher is measured by how well they accomplish their duties for a predetermined period of time in accordance with the standards. Indicators of teacher success include quantity, quality, timeliness, cost-effectiveness, and interpersonal impact. Study variables were measured using the Likert scale, a method for expressing agreement or disagreement with a particular topic, item, or event. On Likert scales, five rating points are usually utilized. Two points were given for disagreeing. A score of 3 was given if there was only a small amount of agreement. Consent was scored on a -point scale. You get five points since I completely agree with you.

3.2. Sampling and Data Collection Technique

In this study, a quantitative methodology was employed, emphasizing the analysis of numerical data (numbers) that had been subjected to statistical processing. Because the population was fairly vast and dispersed across a large geographic area, sampling utilised multistage random sampling. Junior High School teachers in Delhi NCR region, made up the population in the initial phase. Next, permanent teachers who had worked for at least five years and had at least a bachelor's degree or four diplomas were utilised as the target demographic. The choice of the number of research samples was made in accordance with the statement made by Hair et al. (2010), who stated that the sample size for respondents should be adjusted to the number of question indicators on the questionnaire, which ranged from a minimum of 5 to a maximum of 10. Given that there were 16 indicators in this study and an additional indicator of 8, the research sample's size was 300 teachers (16x8). The method of gathering data was sending a questionnaire via Google Form or direct delivery to the respondent (offline) (on line). The usefulness and efficiency of this mixed data collection strategy were taken into consideration.

3.3. Data analysis

Data analysis methods included Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) PLS, represented by Smarth PLS software, and PLS Graph. According to Solimun et al. (2017), the stages for data analysis using SEM-PLS are as follows: establishing a structural model (Inner model); designing a measurement model (Outer model); creating path diagrams; and assessing goodness of fit. Given that the data distribution in this model was not

problematic and that the measurement scale may be nominal, ordinal, interval, or ratio, the use of SEM-PLS was chosen.

The t statistic had to be greater than 1.96 in order for the hypothesis to be accepted because the alpha 5% statistic for testing the used hypothesis was 1.96. The probability with a p-value of 0.05 was employed as the standard for adopting a hypothesis.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Results

Four factors were included in this study: teacher performance (Y), organisational culture (Z1), organisational commitment (Z2), and transformational leadership (X), which served as the independent and mediating variables, respectively. The four factors that made up the transformational leadership variable were ideal influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual awareness. The four factors that made up the organisational culture variable were adaptation, achievement, clan, and bureaucracy. Five factors, including quantity, quality, timeliness, cost effectiveness, and interpersonal relationships, made up the teacher performance variable.

4.1.1. Result of Outer Model Test

To verify that the applied measurements are useable (valid and reliable) as measurements, we employed the analysis of the external model. We discovered connections between latent variables and their indices by studying this model. Convergence validity, discriminant validity, and configuration confidence were tested on external models. Standardized loading factors that describe the association between each measure (indicator) and its components show that convergent validity tests are based on correlations between item scores and component scores. We looked at the metrics. Individual reflectance was deemed high if they showed a correlation of >0.7 with the construct being tested, while external exposure values between 0.5 and 0.6 were deemed adequate. The outcome of the convergent validity test for the reflective measurement model on transformational leadership, organisational culture, organisational commitment, and teacher performance revealed that the loading factor indicator value was greater than 0.700, indicating that the indicators for the variables had been met.

The discriminant validity test is a reflecting indicator measuring methodology based on the construct's cross-loading value. If their structure correlation with gauge is higher than that of other structures, then their block size is superior to that of other blocks. Also, comparing the square root of the sampled mean variance (AVE) values is a means to evaluate the discriminant's validity.

According to the results of the discriminant validity test using AVE root scores, the

variables Transformational Leadership, Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment, and Teacher Performance were all satisfied because the AVE root scores (bold) were higher than the correlation values between the latent variables. It was finished. The structures seen in the Latent Variable Coefficients view are measured using the Structure Confidence Test. Internal consistency and Cronbach's alpha are two of her measurement techniques for evaluating the dependability of composites. The construct is deemed reliable if the achieved value is greater than 0.70. It is possible to enhance the combined reliability result by using Cronbach's alpha. The variable can be regarded as dependable if the Cronbach alpha value is higher than 0.70.

According to the reliability test results using the composite reliability value and the Cronbachs Alpha value, each variable for transformational leadership, organisational culture, organisational commitment, and teacher performance has achieved construct reliability with a test value of more than 0.70.

4.1.2. Test Results

Based on entity theory, internal model analysis described the connections between latent variables. While assessing the inner model with PLS, we first took the R-squared for each dependent latent variable into account (Partial Least Squares). Despite the fact that the interpretation matched the regression interpretation. To evaluate the impact of a certain independent latent variable on the dependent latent variable in this situation, the change in R-squared value can be used. The findings of the coefficient of determination test reveal an R-squared value of 0.576 for the influence of transformational leadership on organisational culture. This suggests that transformative leadership accounts for 57.6% of the impact on organisational culture, with other factors accounting for the remainder. An R-squared value of 0.365 was obtained from a coefficient of determination test that looked at how transformational leadership affects organisational commitment. This indicates that transformative leadership can account for 36.5% of the impact on organisational commitment, with other factors accounting for the remainder.

An R-squared value of 0.600 was obtained through coefficient tests that looked at the effects of organisational culture, leadership change, and organisational involvement on teacher performance. This suggests that creative leadership, organisational culture, and organisational engagement account for 60.0% of the impact on teacher performance, with other factors accounting for the remaining portion.

4.1.3. Hypothesis Testing Results

We can observe the t-statistics and probability values in hypothesis testing. The t-statistic will be used to test the hypothesis, and an alpha of 5% will be used as the acceptance condition if the t-statistic is greater than 1.96. On the other hand, when the p-value is

lower than 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted using probability. The outcomes of hypothesis testing using path coefficients, t-statistics, and p-values are discussed as follows.

We can observe that transformative leadership significantly enhances teacher performance. A path coefficient of 0.356, a t statistic of 2.630, and a P-value of 0.009 are used to illustrate this. This leads to the conclusion that teachers perform better when they have stronger transformative leadership skills. Moreover, favourable and significant effects of transformational leadership on teacher performance in corporate culture were discovered. A path coefficient of 0.237, a t-statistic of 2.860, and a P-value of 0.004 are used to illustrate this. As a result, organisational culture seems to be a key and beneficial mediator of the effects of transformative leadership on teacher performance.

By organisational involvement, transformational leadership has been demonstrated to have a favourable and significant effect on teacher performance. This is depicted by a 0.133 path coefficient, a 2.925 t-statistic, and a 0.004 P-value. So, it suggests that organisational commitment will have a positive and significant influence on the impact of transformational leadership on teacher performance.

4.2. Discussion

4.2.1. The effectiveness of teachers is influenced by transformational leadership

As everyone is aware, a teacher's success is measured by how well he or she performs the tasks assigned to him or her during the course of a certain learning process. Among other things, the organization's governance and leadership practises can result in improved performance. According to Robins and Judge (2015), a number of elements, such as leadership style, organisational culture and organisational commitment, are responsible for the rising individual performance.

The leader role determines how well organisation members function in terms of leadership style. This is due to the fact that leaders' social behaviour, which encourages subordinates to recognise, understand, and put into practise organisational principles and values, determines how an organization's members will behave (Yulk, 2015; Luthan, 2015). Because of this, leaders must be able to select a style of leadership that is seen to be effective at influencing the behaviour of organisational members. Leadership that is transformational must be able to connect the organization's members to the future vision. They must have the ability to persuade their subordinates to perform their jobs in the organization's best interests rather than just their own. As a result, principals' transformative leadership is crucial for raising teacher performance. According to research by Alzoraiki et al. (2018) and Andriani et al. (2018), transformational leadership has a favourable and significant impact on teacher performance, which is compatible with the reason provided.

Also, leaders who employ a transformational leadership style pay attention to and value their followers, making them feel important to the organisation and fostering momentum for their followers to contribute as effectively as possible. Consequently, the Principal must be diligent in putting transformational leadership into practise in order to manage teachers effectively and get the best performance levels from them.

4.2.2. Organizational culture has an impact on teacher performance under transformational leadership.

The study's findings demonstrate that organisational culture, not just management style, has an impact on teachers' performance. This implies that enhancing company culture while implementing intense transformational leadership can improve teacher performance. Employee involvement in the shape of performance necessitates leadership in the form of guidance, inspiration, and support. Direct support from leaders for employee success is also possible, as is strengthening company culture. In this situation, transformational leadership can influence subordinates to put the needs of the organisation ahead of their own. For this reason, it is thought that implementing transformational leadership in schools may be able to contribute to an improvement in teacher performance.

A leadership strategy that is appropriate for teachers' qualities is needed in efforts to get the best performance out of teachers. Because of the high level of education among the organization's members (teachers), transformational leadership is thought to be the best approach to apply in educational institutions. According to Hater and Bass (1988), highly educated people are more drawn to transformational leadership because they want for professional and personal growth-enhancing work challenges. Nevertheless, motivation, organisational culture, organisational commitment, and organisational design with diverse relationship patterns are additional factors that influence individual performance in addition to transformational leadership. 2015's Robins and Judge.

The application of transformational leadership and the bolstering of organisational culture can be used to successfully accomplish performance as a means of member contribution to the organisation. According to Masa'deh et al. (2016), transformational leadership can boost an employee's willingness to complete work that results in optimal performance and thus, higher satisfaction and performance. It is crucial to realise that a person's conduct at work is influenced not only by the leadership style but also by personal characteristics, and that the operating system has a significant impact on how tasks are carried out. According to Olaleye and Oluremi's (2013) research, there is a strong and positive association between teacher performance and eight human resource activities (recruitment, selection, induction, self-development, pay, mentorship, and leadership). The leadership, organisational culture, and competence of school principals all have a favourable and

significant impact on teacher performance, according to research by Kanya et al. (2021).

4.2.3. By organisational commitment, transformational leadership affects student performance in the classroom

The findings of this study show that organisational commitment affects teacher effectiveness through transformational leadership. The deployment of rigorous transformational leadership and increased organisational commitment can therefore be used to improve teacher performance. In order for organisation members to perform as a kind of contribution, leaders must provide clear instructions, inspiration, and role models to inspire them to participate as effectively as possible. This procedure can be carried out by putting transformational leadership into practise together with bolstering organisational commitment. According to research, organisational dedication and leadership style have a favourable impact on employee performance (Ennis et al., 2018).

Leaders who employ a transformational leadership approach show their followers that they are valued and appreciated, which in turn increases their loyalty to the organisation (Mc Laggan et al. 2013). When workers feel valued for their efforts, they are more likely to give their best to the company. Since commitment, a form of employee participation in an organisation, calls for leaders to provide orientation, incentive, and role models. Among other methods, this process can be carried out through putting transformational leadership into practise and bolstering organisational commitment. Several studies have discovered a relationship between organisational commitment and transformational leadership (Allen et.al., 2017; Pratama et.al., 2020).

Building a culture of cooperation, employee professionalism, and efficient problem-solving can be facilitated by using a transformational leadership paradigm. The findings of a study by Gulluce et al. (2016) demonstrate that transformational leadership has a significant beneficial impact on organisational commitment, even serving as the primary predictor of higher levels of commitment (Senjaya and Anindita, 2020). As a result, the use of transformational leadership increases teachers' organisational commitment, which in turn improves their performance. So, in order to effectively improve teacher performance, schools must employ transformational leadership through bolstering organisational commitment.

5. Conclusion and Implication

The effectiveness of teachers is crucial in raising educational standards. Innovative leadership, a strong corporate culture, and organisational dedication can all support improving teacher performance. The role of transformational leadership as an unbiased variable may have a significant direct or indirect impact on teacher performance. A key

mediator of the effect of transformative leadership on teacher performance is the presence of organisational culture and organisational commitment. Consequently, transformational leadership can be consistently applied, together with enhancing organisational culture and organisational commitment, to increase teacher performance. In order to expand on prior understanding, research findings have implications that involve adding organisational culture and organisational commitment as mediating variables in the development of research models. The findings of this study further promote the advancement of human resource management knowledge by demonstrating that organisational commitment, organisational culture, and transformational leadership all significantly and favorably affect teacher performance.

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